

**THE ANALYSIS OF SELECTION AND TRAINING MODEL
IN EFFORTS TO INCREASE EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE
PT. ARZURO HR PERFORMANCE**

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ABSTRACT

The study conducted at PT Arzuro Kinerja SDM aims to prove empirically the effect of selection and training on employee performance, both partially and simultaneously. The method used in the study was descriptive quantitative, with multiple regression analysis. The independent variable of the study uses Selection (variable X1) and Training (variable X2), while the dependent variable of the study uses Employee Performance (variable Y). The sample used in the study was 100 saturated samples, which were taken directly through a questionnaire of 100 respondents. Hypothesis testing shows that selection and training have significant positive effect on employee performance, both partially and simultaneously. The regression model of the research results $Y = 0.147 + 0.864X1 + 0.158X2$.

Keywords: Selection, Training, Employee Performance

PROEM

Employee performance, is one indicator that is used to see the extent to which employees are accomplished, professional, competent and characterized. In various research results, performance has always been the main focus, because the impact of performance has a great influence on both the organization and individual employees. Based on BPS data that the quality of the workforce in Indonesia is still dominated by unskilled laborers with elementary school education, this was recorded in 2015 at 95,621 while the workforce with S1 education was only 31,426. Therefore it is not surprising if the Indonesian labor force occupies many positions at the labor level of 148,537 in 2015.

The results of research conducted by the Regional Research and Development Agency in 2016 at Kutai Kartanegara Regency, the competitiveness of local labor in the management ranks is very small. where at the top management level only 23% while foreign workers amounted to 77%, at the middle management level of 38% while foreign workers were 62% and at the low management level of 49% while foreign workers were 51%. Furthermore local workforce is also weak in terms of discipline, work performance, level of education, work skills, and quality of work with an average value of 1.33.

The above phenomenon is the basis for conducting this research. Where research will be conducted at PT. Arzuro HR Performance. The unit of analysis in this study is all employees of PT. Arzuro HR Performance by providing a questionnaire as a research instrument.

THEORETIC

Performance

Performance is the achievement of employee achievements in the implementation of tasks and work provided (Siswanto, 2009). While Mangkunegara (2000) explains the factors that can influence the achievement of performance, namely: knowledge, skills, abilities and motivation. In the Mukrodi study (2018), it was suggested that partial and simultaneous recruitment and selection had a significant effect on the performance of lecturers. The definition and previous research above, confirms that performance is an important variable for the organization, because it is a representative of achieving the organization's vision and mission.

Selection

Selection is the stage of selecting employees. Employees are selected based on certain criteria. Generally it includes quality administration, intellectual competence, emotional competence, and good personality. In addition, at the selection stage employees are tested for interaction and communication skills.

Relationship between selection and employee performance has been explained in a previous study by Potale, et al (2016), where the research findings indicate that recruitment and selection affect employee performance, both partially and simultaneously at PT Bank Sulutgo. Furthermore Oaya, et al (2017) also explains that

selection influences employee performance. Understanding and previous research above, illustrates that selection plays an important role at the stage of employee acceptance. The good selection system, will be able to capture potential people who have personality and superior competence, so that when they become employees they are expected to have good performance.

Training

Training is formal self-development. Usually, it is the demand for non-career jobs or career advancement for an employee, this formal development can be carried out by companies and training institutions (Hasibuan, 2017). Relationship between training and employee performance has been explained in a previous study by Shafiq, S & Hamza, SM (2017), where the results of his research concluded that training had a significant positive effect on employee performance in a private company in Malaysia. Furthermore Triasmoko et al (2014) also explained that training had a significant positive effect on employee performance at PT Pos Indonesia (Persero) Kota Kediri Branch. Explanation of theory and previous research confirms that employees will continue to increase performance when given training. Employees are routinely given new challenges, consciously or not, they will continue to hone their thinking skills and skills, so that in the future they have superior performance and have an impact on achieving organizational goals.

METHOD

The object company research is PT. Arzuro HR Performance, with address Wisma NH1st Floor Jl. Raya Pasar Minggu Kav. 2B-C Pancoran South Jakarta. This research method uses a quantitative approach with descriptive and inferential explanations. The sampling method uses saturated sample techniques by giving questionnaires to 100 respondents. The analytical method used is multiple linear regression (multiple regression analysis) using SPSS 20 statistical tools. The systematic test analysis consists of validity test, reliability test, classic assumption test, hypothesis test and test coefficient of determination. Hypothesis testing using partial hypothesis testing and simultaneous hypothesis testing. Furthermore, the collected data is tabulated and analyzed descriptively. That is explained about the average value of each questionnaire.

RESULT

The results of validity test show that all instruments of the selection, training and performance variables are valid. Similarly, based on reliability tests, shows a reliable value. Valid and reliable research instruments explain that the questionnaire compiled in this study can actually measure the phenomena that are intended to be appointed and have been answered with the truth by the research respondents. Furthermore, the data in this study have met the classical assumptions as a prerequisite in regression analysis. By fulfilling the analysis prerequisites, this data is feasible to be used as research data. The aim is to see or predict the influence of selection and training on employee performance in the future. The following are the results of the analysis:

Table 1. Partial Test

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.147	3.871		.038	.970
selection	.864	.087	.692	9.910	.000
training	.158	.070	.157	2.242	.027

a. Dependent Variable: performance
 Source: Research Data, 2018

Table 2. Simultaneous Test ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	2040.583	2	1020.291	57.647	.000 ^b
Residual	1716.807	97	17.699		
Total	3757.390	99			

a. Dependent Variable: performance
 b. Predictors: (Constant), selection, training
 Source: Research Data, 2018

Based on the data above, it can be stated the following analysis and explanation bellow:

1. The effect of selection on performance

The partial test results show, selection has a significant effect on performance and the regression coefficient is 0.864, the tcount is 9,910 and the significance value is 0,000. This finding means that the selection of a recruitment system has a very high probability of selecting potential people (good performers).

Furthermore, the magnitude of the value of the influence of selection on employee performance at PT Arzuro SDM Performance confirms that the selection system that is applied is really made carefully to see prospective employees who are good personality, good intelligence, socially good and further than that they have good intentions to develop with the company.

The selection instruments applied are written examinations, interviews and medical check-ups. At the written test stage the company prepares material with a portion of 70% to test the level of competence and 30% to test personality. So the questions arranged really see the extent to which reason and reason can respond to various questions. This is intended, if the prospective employees are accepted, they have a good response that nature runs and completes the task.

While at the interview stage, the company wants to see in more detail the personality of the prospective employee. This is important, to see mental readiness in solving various problems wisely. Therefore a series of sensitive questions is asked and a series of creative questions that spur the birth of ideas. Thus it is known about the general description of employees, especially regarding his personality.

A series of tests above were conducted to see the potential potential of the employee, so that the company can easily determine the needs of HR in the future by providing appropriate jobs, the right positions and fair rights. Therefore, it is not surprising if the selection at PT Arzuro HR performance greatly influences the performance of its employees.

2. The effect of training on performance

The partial test results show that training has a significant effect on performance, and the regression coefficient is 0.158, the tcount is 2.242 and the significance value is 0.027. This finding means that training can directly improve

employees' knowledge and skills, which in turn will impact on employee performance in the future.

The interesting thing about this finding is that training has no better effect on the performance of PT Arzuro's HR Performance. Of course this is important to explain. Where the results of observations show, that the training system or training program at PT Arzuro HR performance is indeed not made in certainty in every year and is intended for all employees. The fact is that training is only given to certain employees, and generally to managerial level employees. So no wonder, if the overall performance of employees is not better than the selection.

Then, the next interesting fact is related to the company's seriousness towards the training program. Training at PT Arzuro HR performance has not been seen as a basic need in which every employee must, routinely and entirely participate in training. This is motivated by the type of business at PT Arzuro. HR performance that fundamentally does not require all employees to continuously participate in training programs.

Another interesting thing is that the existing training programs have not run as they should, and the training methods provided have not been packaged in a modern way, making the participants interested and enthusiastic in participating in the training, as well as the implications for increasing employee knowledge and work ability.

3. The effect of selection and training on performance

Simultaneous test results show, selection and training together have a significant effect on performance and the coefficient of determination is 0.543, the value of F count is 57,647 and the significance value is 0,000. This finding has an interpretation that a good selection process and an appropriate training program can statistically improve employee performance with a contribution amount of 0.543 or 54.3%.

This finding is quite good. considering the value of contributions or the influence of joint selection and training on performance more than 50%. This confirms that the selection system as a process of accepting prospective new employees is mandatory and must be done. More than that, the system created must be really compiled based on the right criteria, where the arrangement is

adjusted to each existing position and the criteria depart from organizational values, so that the people who are accepted are truly employees who are personally good, competent and as expected by the company.

After the employee passes the selection process, the next stage is to provide training. Training is the stage of determining employees in the future. How the company mixes the potential of each of its employees, because that is the company will know which employees are performing, committed, loyal and totality towards the organization.

These findings remind every company, especially PT Arzuro HR Performance. That employee performance does not increase by itself, the participation of the company has a large portion, namely through a good selection system and provide training to employees.

Based on the analysis and discussion above, the research findings can be presented as follows:

1. The selection process is very important at the acceptance stage. Because of that, the company will get employees who are competent, professional, integrity, character and high performance. Therefore it is recommended to:
 - a. Have expert consultants in the field of selection.
 - b. Arrange selection SOPs based on the company's vision and mission.
 - c. Make good selection stages (according to company needs), consisting of written examinations (general knowledge exams, special knowledge exams, and personality / psychological tests), practical exams, interviews, health tests, and work agreements.
 - d. Make selection instruments at each stage based on organizational values and job requirements (financial position selection instruments, IT positions, curious positions, HR positions, administrative positions, general positions etc.)
 - e. Each requirement is explained in detail and has a certain score, to facilitate the assessment.
2. Employees who have passed the selection are then developed through a training program. It aims to improve knowledge, experience and work skills, which have

an impact on achieving corporate goals. Therefore the company needs to create an appropriate and targeted training program, as follows:

- a. Having expert consultants in the field of HR development.
 - b. Develop training schedules on an ongoing basis based on the needs and conditions of the company.
 - c. Establish indicators and achievements of job training
 - d. Have professional instructors, are competent and have character
 - e. Provide adequate budget, training facilities and infrastructure
 - f. Prepare training participants
 - g. Arrange random training activities
 - h. Develop training techniques and methods
 - i. Monitor the implementation of the training process
 - j. Develop training evaluations
 - k. Provide feedback
3. Employee performance needs to be given a clear measure, evaluated and given feedback. This, aims to ensure alignment between the system and HR readiness.
 4. The results of the analysis show that selection is the dominant factor. It is hoped that the selection process will become the company's mainstay in obtaining professional and character employees. Thus, improvements in the selection system and type of selection must be up-to-date.

CONCLUTION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion above, conclusions can be made as follows:

1. Selection has a significant effect on performance and the regression coefficient is 0.864, the value of tcount is 9.910 and the significance value is 0.000. With interpretation, if selection has a system and good implementation, it will be able to improve employee performance by 0.864.
2. Training has a significant effect on performance and the regression coefficient is 0.158, the value of tcount is 2.242 and the significance value is 0.027. With interpretation, if training has a good mechanism and implementation, employee performance will increase by 0.158.

3. Selection and training together have a significant effect on performance and the determination coefficient is 0.543, F count is 57,647 and the significance value is 0,000. With interpretation, the existence of selection and training currently has a contribution to improving employee performance by 54.3% while the rest is explained by other factors (compensation, leadership, work environment, benefits, work system, etc.)

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